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HIGHER EDUCATION AMONG THE SCHEDULED CASTES: DISTRICT LEVEL ANALYSIS OF UTTAR PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

Scheduled Castes (SCs) are educationally backward community in India. Educational backwardness of SCs has its relation with socio-economic inequalities internalized in the structure of Indian social order. Thus, the present research paper is an attempt to study the spatial analysis of achievement in higher education among the scheduled castes in Uttar Pradesh. The paper is based on quantitative work of secondary data extracted from Census of India 2001 and Directory of Colleges, UGC 2001-02. Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER), Educational Attainment Rate (EAR) and Discontinue Rate (DR) has been computed for analysing the pattern of higher education at district level with the help of GIS mapping. Analysis of the paper reveals that there is very high variation in GER and EAR among the districts of Uttar Pradesh. Although accessibility to higher education among the SCs has increased in the recent decades, unfortunately, there is very high rate of discontinue in higher education which affects the EAR for SCs. There is a trend of spatial disparity, gender disparity and urban-rural disparity in achievements of higher education among SCs. Finally, from the analysis a conclusion has been drawn as 'higher the proportion of SCs population, lower the GER and EAR' i.e. lower level of achievement in higher education among SCs.

KEYWORDS: Discontinue Rate (DR), Educational Attainment Rate (EAR), Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER), Higher-Education (HE), Scheduled Castes (SCs).

INTRODUCTION

Scheduled Castes (SCs) are considered as one of the most educationally backward community in India. In spite of large number of efforts of government schemes and programmes to facilitate 'equality of opportunity', it has failed to remove the entrenched nature of backwardness and the structural relations and internalized structures of inequality in the society (Vasavi, 2012). In India gross enrolment ratio in higher education for general population is 20.4 percent for 18-23 years of age group, while it is only 12.5 percent for the SCs population (MHRD, 2013). Further, the attainment rate in higher education among SCs is only 4.19 percent of the total SCs student enrolled in higher education in 2000 (Thorat, 2006). In higher education, though, the overall representation is very poor but within this also the SCs is marginalized, with just 2% as non-technical graduates and above, and just 0.7% with technical higher education (Parul, 2014). Dropout rates in higher education, especially among disadvantaged groups such as SCs and STs are higher than their counterpart and the national average (OECD, 2014). The SCs are backward in educational development and achievements with the increase of level of education and increase in the dropout rate also (De and Bhowmick, 2014). Hence, the SCs are still lagging behind when compared to their counterpart (Non-Scheduled population) when it comes to the proportion enrolled in higher education. Thus, the paper has tried to present a district level pattern of achievement i.e. gross enrollment, attainment rate and discontinue rate in higher education among the scheduled castes in Uttar Pradesh. For this present paper a secondary data has been drawn from the Census of India-2001 and Directory of Colleges 2001-02, University Grand Commission (UGC). GER, EAR and DR have been computed for analysing the pattern of higher education at district level. Analysis reveals that there is spatial variation between male-female and urban-rural in higher education among SCs in the study area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Traditionally Indian society is characterised by social exclusion and glaring inequalities structured in terms of hierarchical caste relations which is the bedrock of this society. As per the order of social hierarchy, SCs languish at the lower strata where material deprivation and impurity reinforce one another (Béteille, 1998). Historically, SCs were involved in unskilled and polluting professions like tanneries, scavenging, etc. Resultantly, they were characterised by extensive illiteracy, mass unemployment, low income, backward technology and scarceness of resources of income to survive (Sinha, 1981). Hence, they remain as the victim institutionalised maltreatment. Majority of SCs are having low literacy status which in turn causes for backwardness with illiteracy, low income, landlessness, poverty, etc. In spite of affirmative action with various education as well as development programmes, the status of SCs has not improved to the desired level (Ravi Babu and Chandrasekarayy (2015). As a result they have limited accessibility to higher education and general education.

Velaskar have cited various reasons for the poor performance and access to higher education. These problems include poor socio-economic background and lower quality of schooling at which SCs students have access to in comparison to other student's (Velaskar, 1986). The poor schooling facilities, poverty and lack of economic resources as the important factors for drop out in higher education among SCs women. She has pointed towards the utility of every extra hand for gaining resources. The women are especially subject to the social prejudices in the rural

areas. The lack of financial help and incentives at the early age are the other main reasons (Chanana, 1993). Higher education institutions of all section of the society as well as of weaker sections, has increased over the period of time but the status of the SCs/STs are still far behind as compare to other social groups and average general level of the country (Deva Ram, 2014). Aikara has inferred that the high dropout arises out of a compulsion for employment to feed and support the family (Aikara, 1980).

The constraints of the SC/ST women pursuing higher education reveals that the intensity of the constraints are more in case of the items viz. that the culture in the colleges i.e. the practices are found to be differ and the students are feeling it difficult to adjust with them. Further, the language spoken i.e., dialect and accent in the college and the language of SC/ST women are also affecting the interaction of SC/ST women with others (Jagadeeswari, 2014). Thus, it can be say that a large section of traditionally deprived people of the Indian society is still deprived in higher education today. The problem of their deprivation in higher education has to be linked with their socio-economic background.

RATIONALE

The present study looks into the accessibility, attainment and dropout rate in higher education among the SCs in Uttar Pradesh. There are several studies which reveal that the socio-economic and educational development has been hampered and they stand at the bottom level of educational development and this status still persists today, despite the efforts by the Government of India by providing various schemes and programmes, there is not much change in their status of higher education.

OBJECTIVES: To analyze the achievement in higher education among the SCs in Uttar Pradesh.

HYPOTHESES

- Gross enrollment in higher education has increased after implementation of reservation policy in higher education system.
- High level of discontinue rate in higher education is the result of weaker socio-economic back ground of SCs which finally culminates into low level of attainment rate in higher education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

DATA BASE

The research paper is based on secondary data extracted from Census of India 2001, C-Series tables, and Directory of Colleges Directory of Colleges, University Grants Commission, 2001-02. Besides, government records and reports have been used in order to supplement the analysis.

GROSS ENROLLMENT RATIO (GER)

The following formula defines GER (higher education):

$$\text{GER in HE} = \frac{\text{All Enrolled in Post-Higher Secondary Classes}}{\text{Total Population in 18-23 age group}} \times 100 \text{ (Sinha, 2008).}$$

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT RATE (EAR)

Educational Attainment is the level of educational accomplishment for the specific age group (18-22/23) that is the percentage of persons with the specific educational level in the age group (Sinha, 2008).

$$\text{EAR} = \frac{\text{Total Number of Population who have completed a higher Education degree}}{\text{Total Population in Age-Group 20+}} \times 100 \text{ (Sinha, 2008).}$$

DISCONTINUE RATE (DR)

$$\text{DR} = \frac{(\% \text{ of Attainment in Higher Secondary Level of Education} - \% \text{ of Attainment in Higher Education})}{\% \text{ of Attainment in Higher Secondary Level of Education}} \times 100 \text{ (Sinha, 2008).}$$

LIMITATION

The study is limited to data base of 2001 as Census of India 2011, education data has not been released till date.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

GROSS ENROLLMENT RATIO

The inter-district variation reveals very diverse pattern of GER among SCs in Uttar Pradesh. State level enrollment ratio in higher education among SCs is only 7.74percent while it is 13.29percent for non-scheduled population in Uttar Pradesh.

Source: Computed from Census of India, 2001, C- Series Tables

There is 43.56percent variation in GER among the districts of Uttar Pradesh. The data result reveals that district Mau shows the highest proportion with 17.56percent followed by Ballia (14.00percent), Ghazipur (12.89percent) and Meerut (12.64percent)among districts that have higher GER for the SCs. While on the other end, district Balrampur records the lowest proportion with 2.07percentGER preceded by Lalitpur (2.41percent), Gonda (2.71percent) and Shrawasti (2.80percent).

Map-1 reveals four important regions showing GER pattern for SCs in the study area. First region (most backward) confined to North Central districts along with Nepal broader districts except Lucknow. This region has lowest (less than 5.9 percent) GER. Second and third region (medium) constitutes Eastern and South Western districts showing higher (9.8-13.6 percent) GER. Fourth (Backward) region covers Western districts along with border of Rajasthan, Delhi and Haryana states showing low (5.9 -9.8 percent) GER. Most interestingfact is that district Sonbhadra comes under lowest GER among SCs despite constituting highest proportion (40%) of SCs population. Majority of the districts having higher proportion (15-25 percent) of SCs population has lowest GER among SCs. In other words, higher the SC population, lower the GER among SCs. It is clear that majority of the districts are showing lower GER in higher education among SCs, which are attributed to lower access to higher education, lack of economic resources in the family and educational expense (Chanana, 2000). Although the enrolment is lowest among the poor casual wage labour household in rural and urban area, it is particularly low among the same poor group from the SC/ST/OBC (Sriwastava, and Sinha, 2008).

MALE-FEMALE VARIATION

TABLE-1 INTER-DISTRICT VARIATION (C.V.) IN GROSS ENROLLMENT RATIO AMONG SCS (MALE-FEMALE) IN UTTAR PRADESH			
	All Colleges/Institutions		
	Person	Male	Female%
Uttar Pradesh	7.74%	11.00%	3.77%
Mean	7.48%	10.75%	3.61%
Standard Deviation	3.26%	4.60%	2.34%
Coefficient of Variation	43.56%	42.76%	64.79%

Source: Computed from Census of India, 2001, C- Series Tables

State level variation of GER among districts of Uttar Pradesh for SCs is 43.56 percent. Variation in GER for male is almost same as total GER in the state, while there is a large variation in GER for females among districts of Uttar Pradesh. It is 64.79 percent at the state level. This is attributed to the level of socio-economic and cultural practices among district of Uttar Pradesh. There is large gap of GER between male-female among SCs in Uttar Pradesh. GER of male and female among the SC population is 11.00 percent and 3.77 percent respectively.

The male-female comparison shows that the position of female in case of SCs population is worst as the gap between male and female is widest. This finding can be contextualised from the very fact that generally female education has been linked with marriage and not with a career. While in lower castes, it has been sometimes linked with career because of poor economic background of their family. Such a comparison cannot be justified because historically non-scheduled population enjoyed the benefits of education when compared with the others. Nevertheless, from the policy perspective it is important to determine the gap between social groups. The GER gap between male-female widens in case of rural areas thus showing that position of the female in higher education is poor. There are various factors which are impeding the females in higher education most of which are related to their social position. Further, the condition of SCs women is much worse than others in Indian Society (Rudolph and Rudolph, 1972).

URBAN-RURAL VARIATION

TABLE-2 INTER-DISTRICT VARIATION (C.V.) IN GROSS ENROLLMENT RATIO AMONG SCs (RURAL-URBAN) IN UTTAR PRADESH			
	All Colleges/Institutions		
	Total	Rural	Urban
Uttar Pradesh	7.74%	6.32%	15.82%
Mean	7.48%	6.26%	14.33%
Standard Deviation	3.26%	3.00%	4.72%
Coefficient of Variation	43.56%	47.92%	32.97%

Source: Computed from Census of India, 2001, C- Series Tables

There is large gap in the gross enrollment ratio of rural and urban SC populations in Uttar Pradesh. GER in rural and urban areas is 6.32 percent and 15.82 percent, respectively. The urban-rural comparison reveals that the position of the SCs in urban areas is far better than those in the rural areas. This has been attributed to better availability of higher education institutes in urban areas. Populations belonging to SCs are much less educated and skilled than the non-scheduled population both in rural and urban areas (CABE, 2005). Females belonging to SCs living in rural areas are the most disadvantaged. Overall, both in rural and urban areas, the SCs population are much behind the others (CABE, 2005). An additional fact is that the major sections of SCs are living in rural areas, which make their condition worse for higher education.

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT RATE (EAR)

Table-3 shows that there is a 45.14 percent inter-district variation in attainment rate of higher education among the districts of Uttar Pradesh. State level educational attainment rate in higher education among SC student is only 1.93 percent in Uttar Pradesh.

TABLE-3 INTER-DISTRICT VARIATION (C.V.) IN EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT RATE AND DISCONTINUE RATE IN HIGHER EDUCATION AMONG SCS IN UTTAR PRADESH

	Attainment Rate in Higher Education	Discontinue Rate in Higher Education
Uttar Pradesh	1.93%	74.71%
Mean	1.91%	72.35%
Standard Deviation	0.86%	6.02%
Coefficient of Variation	45.14%	8.32%

Source: Computed from Census of India, 2001, C- Series Tables

The analysis reveals that district Ghaziabad and Meerut have the highest proportion of 3.91 percent of EAR in higher education followed by Auraiya (3.57 percent), Lucknow (3.56 percent) and Kanpur Nagar (3.48 percent).

Source: Computed from Census of India, 2001, C- Series Tables

While district Balrampur reports lowest proportion with 0.58 percent in EAR preceded by Shrawasti (0.65 percent), Gonda (0.73 percent), and Kaushambi (0.73 percent). Rest of the districts are between 1-3 percent of EAR in higher education. Map-2 reveals same pattern of EAR among SCs as in GER (Map-1). North Central districts and districts along with Nepal broader and up to the central southern district (Chitrakoot) except Lucknow has low level (less than 1.4 percent) of EAR. The two regions of Eastern and South Western districts along with Madhya Pradesh boundary are showing higher and highest (more than 2.2 percent & 3 percent) level of EAR. Western districts are showing medium (1.4-2.2 percent) level of EAR. District Sonbhadra falls under low level of EAR despite having highest proportion (40%) of SCs population. In fact districts showing lower EAR in higher education are having higher proportion of SCs population with few exceptions. Thus, it may be said that the region having higher proportion of SCs population also have lower EAR among SCs in higher education. The traditionally disadvantageous group like SCs is far behind the advanced group not only in attaining higher education but traditional deprivation and lack of education make them dually marginalized (Parul, 2014).

DISCONTINUE RATE

Table 2 shows that there is an 8.32 percent inter-district variation in discontinue rate in higher education among SCs among the districts of Uttar Pradesh. State level discontinue rate in higher education for SCs is 74.71 percent of the total enrolled.

Source: Computed from Census of India, 2001, C- Series Tables

District wise scenario of reveals almost uniform pattern of discontinue rate among SCs. District Kausambi shows highest proportion with 84.12 percent of SCs students discontinue to their higher education followed by Ballia (84.03 percent), Mau (83.37 percent), Pratapgarh (82.09 percent) and Azamgarh (81.37 percent). On the other hand, district Hardoi shows the lowest proportion with 60.73 percent of total SCs students discontinuing higher education preceded by Shrawasti (60.94 percent) and Sitapur (61.16 percent). Rest of districts have a DR between 60-80 percent of the total SCs in higher education. Eastern, South-Eastern, North-Eastern and some Western districts are showing highest and higher discontinuerate in higher education.

The above analysis reveals that more than 60 percent SCs students in all the 70 districts are discontinue to their higher education due to various reasons. Comparison between GER, EAR and DR (Maps-1, 2 & 3) reveals that generally, the region (district) having higher GER and EAR also recording higher discontinue rate in higher education among SCs. Thus, it may be said that the higher the SC population, lower the GER and EAR among SCs. Further, Higher the SC population, higher is the discontinue rates among SCs. Generally, discontinuing higher education is the consequence of poor socio-economic condition of the individual. Students from poor, rural areas and from less educated families have lower probability to complete their higher education (Pop-Eleches, 2008). The primary reason for which SCs students discontinue their college is failure in examination; but financial support for them is another important factor (Aikara, 1980). As SCs students hail from a less privileged socio-economic background, it has attributed to higher dropout rate in this category (Weisskopf, 2004).

CONCLUSION

Higher education among SCs suffer from the problems of spatial variations, male-female and urban-rural disparity at district level in Uttar Pradesh. There is a high inter-district variation in GER and EAR in higher education among SCs. Moreover, discontinue rate is very high (75 percent) along with very low inter-district variation (8 percent). GER in higher education is lower at district level with some exception. Unfortunately, EAR is very low among the districts which indicates very high drop-out of SCs students. Generally, rural SC female is worst in terms of GER, EAR and very high discontinue rate in higher education. Urban SC population is in better position than rural area in GER. The districts having larger SCs population, also recording lower GER and EAR along with higher DR. In other words, Higher the SCs population, lower the gross enrolment and educational attainment in higher education along with higher discontinue to higher education among SCs.

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APPENDIX-1									
DISTRICT-WISE GER OF SCS POPULATION, UTTAR PRADESH FOR 18-23 AGE GROUP									
		GER Total Colleges					GER Total Colleges		
SL	District	Persons	Males	Females	SL	District	Persons	Males	Females
1	Saharanpur	9.62	12.61	5.4	37	Lalitpur	2.41	3.47	1.3
2	Muzaffarnagar	8.93	11.85	4.8	38	Hamirpur	7.04	9.76	2.92
3	Bijnor	8.6	11.88	3.88	39	Mahoba	3.96	6.09	1.37
4	Moradabad	5.79	7.79	3.07	40	Banda	6.27	9.38	2.16
5	Rampur	5.34	7.48	2.52	41	Chitrakoot	3.45	5.48	1.15
6	Jyotiba Phule Ngr	5.8	8.96	1.7	42	Fatehpur	6.85	10.33	2.27
7	Meerut	12.64	14.93	9.39	43	Pratapgarh	7.31	12.87	2.26
8	Baghpat	9.66	12.47	5.17	44	Kaushambi	4.63	7.99	0.83
9	Ghaziabad	11.13	12.65	9.01	45	Allahabad	11.93	17.88	5.13
10	Gautam Buddha Ngr	6.13	8.01	3.39	46	Barabanki	3.54	5.31	1.43
11	Bulandshahar	6.77	9.16	3.12	47	Faizabad	6.16	9.71	2.57
12	Aligarh	7.35	9.59	4.03	48	Ambedkar Ngr	11.51	17.3	6.38
13	Hathras	8.77	11.86	4.1	49	Sultanpur	5.41	9.06	1.95
14	Mathura	6.61	9.27	2.76	50	Bahraich	3.16	4.79	1.07
15	Agra	9.32	11.49	6.26	51	Shrawasti	2.8	4.55	0.65
16	Firozabad	11.21	14.15	6.92	52	Balrampur	2.07	3.32	0.61

17	Etah	8.5	11.49	4.11	53	Gonda	2.71	4.39	0.81
18	Mainpuri	10.04	13.23	5.47	54	Siddharth nagar	3.7	6.48	0.98
19	Budaun	3.78	5.47	1.47	55	Basti	6.56	10.56	2.54
20	Bareilly	6.8	8.97	4.05	56	Sant Kabir Nagar	4.73	8.38	1.23
21	Pilibhit	6.11	8.67	2.75	57	Mahrajgan j	6.08	10.26	1.83
22	Shahjahanpur	5.13	7.5	1.89	58	Gorakhpur	8.66	13.28	3.83
23	Kheri	3.73	5.59	1.44	59	Kushinagar	6.24	10.47	2.04
24	Sitapur	3.87	5.58	1.69	60	Deoria	10.12	16.04	4.17
25	Hardoi	5.19	7.42	1.87	61	Azamgarh	10.02	16.79	4.3
26	Unnao	4.38	6.03	2.23	62	Mau	17.56	25.7	9.59
27	Lucknow	11.06	13.42	8.05	63	Ballia	14	21.49	5.82
28	Rae Bareli	4.26	6.51	1.91	64	Jaunpur	9.83	17.41	3.29
29	Farrukhabad	6.99	8.96	4.13	65	Ghazipur	12.89	21.28	4.41
30	Kannauj	4.78	6.18	2.57	66	Chandauli	10.69	16.5	4.42
31	Etawah	12.4	15.56	7.55	67	Varanasi	12.63	18.25	6.14
32	Auraiya	9.84	12.22	6.09	68	Sant Ravidas Ngr	9.21	16.51	1.76
33	Kanpur Dehat	7.87	10.16	4.16	69	Mirzapur	6.36	10.79	1.61
34	Kanpur Nagar	11.28	12.2	9.95	70	Sonbhadra	3.66	5.76	1.56
35	Jalaun	10.11	13.84	4.54	71	Uttar Pradesh	7.74	11.00	3.77
36	Jhansi	9.38	11.67	6.53					

APPENDIX-2**SCHEDULED CASTES %, EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT RATE (EAR) AND DISCONTINUE RATE (DR) IN HIGHER EDUCATION AMONG SCS IN UTTAR PRADESH-2001**

SL	District	SC %	EAR	DR	SL	District	SC %	EAR	DR
1	Saharanpur	21.73	2.4	71.45	37	Lalitpur	24.93	1.01	62.51
2	Muzaffarnagar	13.5	2.19	75.01	38	Hamirpur	22.79	2.2	67.98
3	Bijnor	20.94	2.1	71.74	39	Mahoba	25.78	1.37	63.48
4	Moradabad	15.86	1.92	69.31	40	Banda	20.83	2.11	62.97
5	Rampur	13.38	1.38	71.62	41	Chitrakoot	26.34	0.91	69.8
6	Jyotiba Phule Nagar	17.27	1.75	73.72	42	Fatehpur	25.04	1.46	74.42
7	Meerut	18.44	3.91	69.21	43	Pratapgarh	22.01	1.26	82.09
8	Baghpat	10.98	2.22	78.51	44	Kaushambi	36.1	0.73	84.12
9	Ghaziabad	18.04	3.91	67.86	45	Allahabad	21.58	2.47	79.12
10	Gautam Buddha Nagar	16.31	2.38	64.25	46	Barabanki	26.89	0.76	71.79
11	Bulandshahar	20.21	2.2	63.8	47	Faizabad	22.59	1.53	77.06
12	Aligarh	21.2	2.2	66.45	48	Ambedkar Nagar	24.44	2.56	76.13
13	Hathras	25.2	2.33	63.19	49	Sultanpur	22.25	1.15	76.6
14	Mathura	19.6	2.09	72.47	50	Bahraich	14.39	0.75	68.88
15	Agra	21.78	2.31	76.63	51	Shrawasti	18.39	0.65	60.94
16	Firozabad	18.85	2.81	72.89	52	Balrampur	13.48	0.58	68.45
17	Etah	17.15	2.1	71.56	53	Gonda	15.67	0.73	75.55
18	Mainpuri	19.31	2.48	71.56	54	Siddharth Nagar	16.53	1.02	67.97

19	Budaun	17.09	1	64.69	55	Basti	20.87	1.53	77.27
20	Bareilly	12.65	1.73	73.95	56	St. Kabir Nagar	21.19	1.16	80.08
21	Pilibhit	15.23	1.14	78.01	57	Mahrajganj	19.51	1.36	70.64
22	Shahjahanpur	17.72	1.09	75.05	58	Gorakhpur	22.05	2.14	76.5
23	Kheri	25.58	0.83	64.65	59	Kushinagar	18.12	1.39	76.27
24	Sitapur	31.87	0.99	61.16	60	Deoria	18.19	2.11	79.68
25	Hardoi	31.36	1.48	60.73	61	Azamgarh	25.73	1.9	81.37
26	Unnao	30.64	1.19	72.32	62	Mau	22.74	3.12	83.37
27	Lucknow	21.29	3.56	66.72	63	Ballia	16.46	2.79	84.03
28	Rae Bareli	29.83	0.95	78.21	64	Jaunpur	21.93	1.99	79.4
29	Farrukhabad	16.43	2.07	70.8	65	Ghazipur	21.38	2.82	80.53
30	Kannauj	18.43	1.63	70.55	66	Chandauli	24.29	2.58	75.63
31	Etawah	23.41	3.34	68.06	67	Varanasi	13.88	3.16	75.26
32	Auraiya	27.69	3.57	65.62	68	St. Ravidas Nagar	21.63	1.62	75.45
33	Kanpur Dehat	24.85	1.85	75.52	69	Mirzapur	26.76	1.21	76.88
34	Kanpur Nagar	16.45	3.48	72.86	70	Sonbhadra	41.92	0.88	75.99
35	Jalaun	27.04	3.32	69.55		Uttar Pradesh	21.15	1.93	74.71
36	Jhansi	28.07	3.08	66.67					